

A LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF INTERNET MEMES

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ABSTRACT

The article uses online memes as a lens to examine the complex link between language and digital communication. It explores how memes serve as a distinct mode of linguistic and social expression in online environments. The examination focuses on the linguistic aspects of memes that contribute to the communication of humor, irony, and social commentary, including their syntax, pragmatics, and incorporation of visual elements. By highlighting different linguistic strategies such as wordplay, puns, and the usage of particular speech registers, the article emphasizes how language shapes the memetic framework. It also looks at the semiotic aspect of memes, explaining how textual and visual components combine to convey meaning and elicit responses from online users. Additionally, the study examines how memes change over time and within various online communities.

INTRODUCTION

A characteristic of contemporary digital communication, especially on social media platforms, is the prevalence of internet memes. The goal of the study is to discover important linguistic techniques like humor, syntax, and pragmatics that enable memes to convey meaning by examining both their textual and visual components. Memes' adaptation to cultural and social contexts and their evolution across platforms and audiences are also examined in this research. Memes are a special kind of communication that transcends conventional linguistic limits and profoundly shapes digital conversation, according to the research.

These memes, which frequently have a humorous, sarcastic, or satirical tone, show how language use is changing in the digital age. Although memes are usually thought of as a lighthearted kind of entertainment, they are also a powerful instrument for social commentary, cultural norm reinforcement, and even political discourse [3]. By analyzing the structure, purpose, and semiotic elements of online memes, this paper seeks to offer a linguistic analysis of these phenomena. The study will concentrate on how textual and visual components are combined, how memes serve practical purposes, and how these tools contribute to meaning in digital communication.

METHODOLOGY: In order to assess a sample of online memes gathered from different social media platforms, this study uses a qualitative technique. Using a purposeful sampling technique, memes with text and images were chosen, with an emphasis on those that include unique linguistic components like sarcasm, irony, or puns. Semiotic and pragmatic frameworks serve as the foundation for the investigation, which focuses on how memes use irony and comedy to convey hidden meanings [1]. Every meme was examined for both its visual elements and its literary structure, which included grammar, language register, and the usage of language games. In order to investigate how meaning varies across various social media platforms, the study also takes into account the cultural environment in which the memes are exchanged.

RESULTS:

Syntax and morphology

- *Structure:* memes usually contain simple, often incomplete sentences. The use of non-standard grammar is common, increasing humor and engagement. We face this situation every day, that is, when we communicate by phone.

- *Morphology:* word-forming processes such as mixed (e.g. "spork") and mixed (e.g. "manspreading") are common in memes [2]. This leads to the fact that we have a shortening of words.

Social Consequences

- *Community building:* memes develop a sense of belonging and shared understanding among users. That is, in this it helps us to quickly and easily understand short words.

- *Social commentary:* memes are powerful tools for social commentary, reflection and formation of public opinion [2]. Words used by local people are widely used.

Semantics

- *Meaning:* memes often rely on a double entendre and play on words to convey layered meanings. That is, through one word in this one can understand the meaning of the whole-headed sentence.

- *Metaphor and metonymy:* these are often used to create jokes and briefly convey complex ideas. This situation will help to expand our view of the world.

DISCUSSION: Linguistic creativity in memes reflects broader trends in digital communication, where brevity and humor are appreciated. Memes serve as mirrors for society, covering current events, cultural norms, and social tensions in a digestible format. The non-standard language used in memes defies traditional linguistic norms and emphasizes the dynamic nature of language [4]. These cases are spreading widely through new technology and the internet and are serving as public words or abbreviations. In our current colloquial oral and written form. This is also the reason for breaking language norms.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the complex linguistic features of internet memes and their role in contemporary communication. Memes are not only a form of entertainment, but also a rich field for linguistic and social analysis. Internet-based memes are an important part of modern internet communication as entertainment objects that are spread virally through social media and other internet platforms and invite participation and contribution from their audience. They are used by teenagers in their 20s, called millennials, and by teenagers who create and

share memes and engage with them by commenting, criticizing, and recreating them. This is becoming a common way of communicating and speaking among teenagers in everyday conversation. Future research can explore the evolution of memes over time and their effects on language change. At the same time, we must not forget that such abbreviations mean meaning by entering us into our daily vocabulary. And such situations cause the formation of new words.

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